

MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN KIDNEY PARAMETERS DURING CHEMOTHERAPY WITH LIVER POISONING

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Relevance. With liver disease, the development of pathological changes in the kidneys is now beyond any doubt. A number of authors (Rufanov, Shoffar, etc.) described the so-called hepatic-renal syndrome, in which the primary factor causing kidney damage is liver disease. As for kidney damage in parenchymal hepatitis, we have not found comprehensive descriptions of changes in kidney function in this disease in the literature available to us, nor have we found indications of the mechanism of kidney changes in parenchymal hepatitis. Kidney damage in jaundice is caused by bile acid salts. However, a number of data suggest that changes in the kidneys are caused not so much by bile acid salts in jaundice, but rather by the consequences of a profound violation of liver function. According to the clinical observations of a number of authors, kidney damage in jaundice is observed already in the first days of its appearance. The amount of urine decreases, diuresis becomes negative, cylinders, protein and red blood cells appear in the urine.

An increase in residual blood nitrogen. Reduced reserve alkalinity of the blood, often a drop in the alkaline reserve of up to 20%. All these changes are certainly important for kidney function, as they largely determine the conditions in which the kidneys work. During the period of severe jaundice, the daily amount of urine decreases. Lowering the amount of urine to 200-300 cm³ per day. There were often sharp discrepancies between the drunk liquid and the excreted urine, reaching up to 1500 cm³. At the same time, there may be delays in the release of water and its impregnation of tissues. Thus, the McClure test, which, with severe jaundice in patients, was on average equal to 38 minutes, after the onset of jaundice, lengthened to 55 minutes. To find out the causes of fluid retention, it is necessary to measure chlorides in the blood and urine. At the height of the disorder of water metabolism, in some cases we get a slight delay in urinary chlorides, in most cases the release of chlorides is not disturbed. Blood chlorides, both during the period of jaundice increase, its convergence, and after recovery, fluctuated within normal numbers.

And also, biochemical changes in the blood, due to impaired liver and cardiovascular system functions, leading to a violation of acid-base balance-acidosis, do not remain indifferent to the kidneys.

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